

Research Article

Sustainable Development and Water Conservation

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Abstract

Sustainable development is development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. Water conservation refers to reducing the usage of water and recycling of waste water for different purposes like domestic usage, industries, agriculture etc. The concept of Sustainable development has a focus on economic development, social development and environmental protection for future generation. This presentation highlights about the importance, saving water for a Sustainable future and methods of water conservation.

Keywords: Sustainable, development, water, conservation, need, important.

Introduction

Sustainable development is an organizing principle that aims to meet human development goals while also enabling natural systems to provide necessary natural resources and ecosystem services to humans. The concept of Sustainable development has a focus on economic development, social development and environmental protection for future generation. Sustainable development is defined as a constraint upon present consumption in order to ensure that future generations will inherit a resource base that is no less than the inheritance of the previous generation. Human demands are increasing day by day but natural resources are limited. water conservation means avoiding water scarcity. It includes all the policies, strategies and activities to sustainably manage the natural resources of fresh water to protect the hydrosphere and to meet the current and future human demand. Sustainable development of water resources refers to reducing the usage of water and recycling of waste water for different purposes such as cleaning, manufacturing and agricultural irrigation in such a way that water demands of future generations are not hampered. Water is the most important necessity of life for all the living beings on the earth. Without water life is not possible. If we save water now, we are helping to ensure a water supply adequate for future generations. Water sustainability refers to the maintenance and availability of clean water that can continue to fuel future generations for consumption, agricultural processes and biodiversity. However, our water supply is facing a distinct number of challenges. The agricultural industry is currently the largest consumer of freshwater due to its immense need for irrigation, as well as for livestock. Water is a critical natural resource for humankind and the future of our planet. Although water is our largest natural resource, it's both finite and irreplaceable. That's why water sustainability is vital to the future well-being of humans, marine conservation and socio-economic development.

Objective

1. To study the sustainable future.
2. To study the importance of environment.
3. To study the need and importance of water conservation.

Needs and Importance: Water is an important natural resources. All the organisms depend on water to live and grow. 97% Of earth's surface in covered with water and only 3% of water is safe and drinkable. Water is a renewable resource and is used in every work. The ground water is used for drinking, however, it is present in less amount and decreasing day by day.

Water conservation means avoiding water scarcity. water conservation is the practice of using water efficiently to reduce unnecessary water usage. It refers to the development, control and preservation of water resources both ground water and surface. water conservation reduces the use of energy and even helps save household expenditures. Most families pay to use water in their regions or cities. The less water use, the less need to pay every time. If you save water it can save your money bills. We need it for many things including drinking, cooking, cleaning, agriculture purpose, used in industries etc. Conserving water is important because we cannot survive without it. Without water life is not possible. Water is the main source of all lives here. All plants, animals and human beings need water to stay alive. But human beings depend on water more than plants and animals. Water is the protecting the environment. Reducing water use also reduces carbon footprint. Using less water, it protects our ecosystem and wildlife. We conserve more and more water and prevent it for the next generations as well.

Water is very important for every one living in this world. Water is a huge part of our daily lives and without it you cannot live. Our daily activities are so much dependent on water that we cannot even live without water for a single day. Water is essential for life and it is very important to save water. It is very important to realize water conservation benefits and also to implement those in our day to day life.

Saving water helps to preserve our environment. It is simply impossible to imagine human life without water. water conservation encompasses the policies, strategies and activities to manage fresh water as a sustainable resource and efforts to protect the water environment while maintaining a balance between current and future human demand.

Conserving the water minimizes the effects of water shortages and helps us to build a better defense against future drought years. If we save water now, we are helping to ensure a water supply adequate for future generations. Water is the most important source of life on earth because we need water to fulfill all the activities life. Climate change is irreversibly affecting water accessibility as extreme weather events increase, leading to more droughts and floods. Similarly, pollution, growing demand and depletion of our much-needed aquifers are threatening the welfare of all living things, from plants to humans.

Water is key to improving global health and productivity — which means so is water sustainability. Read on to learn more about how water conservation practices can help combat the climate crisis and strengthen socio-economic systems.

Methodologies: We should save the water by using various methods.

1. Recreation of water sources.
2. Adopting water conservation habits.
3. Protection of water from pollution.
4. Sustainable use of ground water- It means uses water in a manner that it meets the present needs of the organism but also made it available to the future generation.
5. Turn off the tap when not in use.
6. Check for leaks.

7. Rain water harvesting- Rain water is a very effective method of conserving natural water and replenishing the groundwater level. In this method of conservation of water, the rain water is collected and allowed to percolate into a deep pit or a reservoir, so that it seeps down and improves the ground water table.
8. Water metering- Another efficient way of cutting down water wastage is to install water meters and measure the amount of water that is being used in residential and commercial buildings.

Conclusion: Water is an essential natural resources. But now a days it gets polluted and the level of groundwater and surface water is decreasing day by day. To conserve water many methodologies and habits adopted by people for its conservation. If you save water if can save your money bills. Reduction in interior water use cuts waste water flows, especially over flowing of gutters which contaminates the environment. Environment benefits include ecosystem and habitat protection. Water conservation helps in improving the quality of drinking water. Water is the most important necessity of life for all the living beings on the earth. Without water no one can exist even for a day. We know that there is very less percentage of clean water available on the earth. We should not waste clean water and save it for future generation.

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